

Rise from the ashes: Rejuvenating Cavite coffee farm caused by Taal volcano eruption

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Abstract

This paper discusses the implementation of a roadmap rejuvenation plan carried out by non-governmental organizations and Cavite farmers in a damaged biodiversity. The foundation of our work was influenced by a methodological guide for a roadmap rejuvenation plan and procedures used in a descriptive correlational analysis. To make the rejuvenation strategy clear, we suggest an investigative mechanism that perceives structures of reflexive and learning experience. Descriptive research design assisted researchers in seeing how coffee farmers evaluated and looking for organizations to work with in creating a roadmap rejuvenation plan with improved pertinence and reception in revitalizing the coffee farm and coffee production in Cavite, Philippines. The following are the key findings and recommendations at the process stage. It is critical to establish organizations to lead an innovative and complex roadmap plan to restore a land that has been destroyed by a volcano eruption. The study's findings allow us to improve the methodological aspects of coffee farm planning, execution, and rejuvenation.

Keywords: Coffee, rejuvenation, roadmap plan, *kapeng barako*, Amadeo.

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Introduction

Amadeo, Cavite is dubbed the "Coffee Capital of the Philippines" because it accounts for 67 percent of *kapeng barako* production in CALABARZON (Region IV-A) and has gained popularity among tourists as well (Lopez, 2020). Coffee is the most affected commodity amid the eruption of the Taal volcano, according to a news report by Rita (2020). The eruption left a lasting impression on Amadeo's coffee industry.

The coffee industry has always been resilient. Due to its high demand, coffee beans have become a staple of many countries' economies. Numerous businesses and livelihoods have benefited from coffee. Resilience has been critical to thriving in the face of diversity and challenges such as natural disasters, climate change, pandemics, and supply shortages (Baker, 2009; Congress of the Philippines, 2009; Sajise et al., 2012; Woodside, 2011). Many have thrived by adapting to this diversity, but the Philippine Coffee Industry's resilience and sustainability remain a significant challenge. As a result, metrics such as marketing and support systems have yet to be developed to increase the coffee's resilience in the face of adversity (Buclatin, 2018; Tan, 2021).

The business has used a variety of promotional materials over the years to reach its end users with its products. Nowadays, additional farms have been established to meet the demand for coffee beans in the country's restaurants and hotels. Amadeo is not only a supplier to neighboring towns and provinces, but also to the country's capital, Manila. Whereas this most urbanized region has the highest coffee exportation and demand. Despite the high quality of their products and services, many farmers, coffee producers, coffee retailers, and coffee shops face difficulties in promoting their products and services, particularly in the

aftermath of the Taal Volcano Eruption. There are specific challenges they are currently facing in terms of promoting their coffee and gaining market trust.

Thus, recognizing the difficulties that the coffee business is currently facing would aid in the development of additional solutions and marketing plans that will assist farmers in regaining their livelihood income while also allowing the business to offer the highest quality coffee in a larger market. In order to remain competitive in the coffee industry, sustainability must be tailored for each value chain player (Second Cordillera Highland Agricultural Resource Management Project, 2019). The process of being reborn or given new energy is known as rejuvenation. The damage caused by the Taal Volcano eruption has made a significant impact on Amadeo Cavite coffee farms.

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- rejuvenate the Cavite coffee farm caused by Taal Volcano eruption, and ascertain into which stage is Cavite Coffee Industry after the volcano eruption as a basis to develop a roadmap rejuvenation plan;
- improve quality of coffee appropriate post-harvest technologies; Consumption and Promotion of Pahimis Coffee (Kapeng Amadeo);
- increase productivity and production;
- improve farmers' standard of living through diversified high value agriculture;
- increase rural employment;
- lessen coffee bean and coffee products importation; and
- improve income of farmers, processors and other stakeholders.

Hence, this study was conducted among local coffee industries in a coffee-producing Hence, this study was conducted among local coffee industries in a coffee-producing municipality in Amadeo, Cavite, Philippines.

Another concept that is similar to the roadmap rejuvenation plan is community communication. Participatory development communication (PDC) is defined by Bessette (2004) as a "*planned activity based on participatory processes and the use of media and interpersonal communication to facilitate dialogue among diverse stakeholders about a common development problem or opportunity.*" PDC's goal is to create and execute a series of activities that lead to the solution or realization of a development project, as well as those that help and accompany it.

Group communication, participatory communication, and participatory decision-making (PDC) are three principles that enable collective action and community engagement by involving the use of communication strategies and tools designed to steer group dynamics. Apart from local residents, "group engagement" refers to promoting the active participation of various actors or members in the community, such as development and research agents, decision-makers, local representatives, and non-government organizations (NGOs).

Given the nature of group engagement, participatory communication, and participatory decision-making, these are essential factors for enhancing the capacity of local community members, such as farmers, to gain understanding and knowledge of local concerns, shape opinions, and make informed decisions (Coldevin, 2003; Ongkiko & Flor, 1998). Public networking, participatory communication, and participatory decision-making are often used to communicate cultural practices throughout the community.

Assuming that local people, such as community decision-makers such as local leaders and politicians, research and extension agents, non-government employees, and others, are the "doers" and "influencers" of growth in the region, community communication's importance is based on its position in assisting local people in becoming more capable. This occurs as people have access to and learn information and knowledge that allows them to have a greater understanding of community problems and events. This improved understanding then aids people in forming opinions, which lead to informed decisions and, in

turn, serve as the foundation for collective action. This is one planned project, according to community engagement, participatory communication, and PDC.

The word "group communication" is used in this study to refer to the meanings and structures provided by all three concepts listed previously.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study on coffee farmers' engagement in rejuvenating plan in Amadeo, Cavite, Philippines.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

The input involves coffee farmers' socio-demographic characteristics and their level of engagement in community communication, the farm-related profile and their level of engagement in community communication, and their media use. The process includes four strategies for road map rejuvenating plan based on Pablo (2016): Plantation and post-harvest technology development, processing performance improvement skills trainings on coffee processing, promotion and marketing enhancement, and the creation of sustainable and enabling environment.

1. Plantation and post-harvest technology development

- Benchmarking and cross visits
- Skills development trainings
- Distribution of coffee seedlings: Collaborated with provincial local government units (PLGUs), non-government organizations (NGOs), Department of Agrarian Reform (DAR-RFU); National Greening Program – Department of Environment and Natural Resources (NGP-DENR)

- New plantations
 - Convergence with DENR, NGOs, PCA Info materials distributed as ready references of the farmers
2. Processing performance improvement skills trainings on coffee processing
- Coffee 102; Barista 101; Quality Improvement Trainings – Cupping Lessons, Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP), Philippine National Standard (PNS), Good Agricultural Practice (GAP); Food and Drug Administration (FDA) Licensing and Product Certification / Food Safety Trainings
 - On established coffees: Department of Health – Food and Drug Administration – Department of Trade and Industry (DOH-FDA-DTI) Partnership; Cupping Sessions for the assessment of coffee quality; Benchmarking on Coffee Processing
3. Promotion and marketing enhancement
- Trade fairs and exhibits
 - Coffee products at the Regional One Town, One Program (OTOP) / pasalubong centers
 - Market matching activities – Packaging and label design
 - Trade / entrepreneur trainings conducted – visual merchandising, pricing and costing
 - Coffee Small and Medium Enterprise directories that led buyers tour the coffee regions
 - Geographical indication project
 - Consultancy program with international coffee experts
 - Live guesting on Negosyo Atbp. with Research and Development (R&D) / small and medium enterprises (SMEs)
 - Press conferences and social media promotions
4. Creation of sustainable and enabling environment
- Organization of the regional and provincial coffee clusters and conduct of periodic meetings
 - Strategic planning at all levels including Intra-DTI at the national level
 - Annual value chain analysis and upgrading plus greening
 - Mainstreaming
 - Aligning and participation to the projects for coffee
 - Coffee investment / business opportunities / regional industry profiling

Methodology

The descriptive-correlational research design was used in this analysis. This research used a case study method, which entails delving into specific aspects of a phenomenon. The phenomenon studied was coffee farmers' participation in a roadmap rejuvenation plan as they adjusted their farming practices in the aftermath of the Taal Volcano eruption in Amadeo, Cavite.

The research was carried out in Amadeo, a municipality in the province of Cavite's sixth district. Amadeo is known as the "Coffee Capital of the Philippines," as it is an upland, fourth-class municipality (based on income). The research took place from October 2020 to March 2021.

Amadeo was divided into four quadrants for the survey: northeast, southeast, southwest, and northwest. For representativeness, the barangay with the most coffee farmers from each of Amadeo's geographic parts was chosen. Banaybanay, Maitim, Talon, and Poblacion are the barangays in question. From these barangays, ninety-three survey respondents were chosen at random.

Informants/interviewees for the main informant interview (KII) were purposefully selected and included those with knowledge of and participation in coffee farming in the region.

The 12 key informants were distributed as follows:

- Three (3) representatives from NCB (National Coffee Board)
- Two (2) officers of Amadeo Coffee Growers Association
- One (1) manager of Cafe Amadeo Development Cooperative
- One (1) municipal agricultural officer
- Four (4) agricultural technicians
- One (1) farmer scientist on coffee (also from Amadeo)

This research used both qualitative and quantitative data collection approaches. Key informant interviews (KII), and a survey were used. There were two parts of the interview schedule. Part I inquired about respondents' socio-demographic characteristics; Part II inquired about their observations of the state of the coffee industry and its effects in their region, as well as adaptation of their farming practices to; and Part III inquired about their observations of the state of the coffee industry and its effects in their area.

In this research, descriptive analysis was used. The responses were evaluated and categorized based on rational themes. The survey's results were provided in the form of means, frequencies, and percentages. The information gathered was compared to structures for a roadmap rejuvenation plan, participatory communication, and participatory growth communication.

Results and Discussion

Summarizing the findings on the various parameters of proposed rejuvenation roadmap plan is described as follows:

- A. Improve quality and availability of planting material
- B. Enhance farm efficiency and investments
- C. Improve market price and coffee standards
- D. Financing: Access to long term funds
- E. Logistics: Reduce logistics cost to processors' market
- F. R&D: Improve search and extension services
- G. Policies: Appropriate investment incentives
- H. Market intelligence: Reliable industry data
- I. Organization: Industry unity in diversity

The major terms of reference will be determined by the completion of the Master Plan/Roadmap:

The following principles are crucial: GAP results in high farm revenue due to good farm yields. Green bean self-sufficiency is expected to be achieved and maintained by 2017 if farmers earn a good return from coffee relative to alternative crops. The farmers, the commercial sector, government-backed civil society organizations (CSOs), local government units (LGUs), and state universities and colleges (SUCs) will all work together to drive growth (Tan, 2021).

Conclusion

According to the findings, providing a clear roadmap rejuvenation plan after the Taal Volcano eruption would have had a significant impact on the Amadeo coffee industry, leading them down a path that would enable them to cope with the disruption.

Community involvement of coffee farmers

To ensure the coffee farming industry's long-term viability in Amadeo, the local government and municipal agriculture office are encouraged to work with Cavite State University (CvSU) – possibly the National Coffee Research, Development and Extension Center (NCRDEC) – to find ways for the younger generation to get interested in coffee farming. According to the findings of this report, Amadeo's coffee farming population is ageing, which could be detrimental to the country's coffee industry.

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